

NIW: A Net2Plan-based Library for NFV over IP over WDM Networks

José Luis Romero-Gázquez¹, Miquel Garrich¹, Francisco-Javier Moreno Muro¹,
María-Victoria Bueno Delgado¹ and Pablo Pavón Mariño^{1,2},

¹Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena, Plaza del Hospital, 1, 30202 Cartagena, Spain

²E-lighthouse Networks Solutions, Calle Ángel s/n, 30202 Cartagena, Spain

e-mail: {josel.romero, miquel.garrich, javier.moreno, mvictoria.bueno, pablo.pavon}@upct.es

ABSTRACT

Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) technologies enable a major technological breakthrough for telecom operators' networks. In this paper, we present the NFV over IP over WDM (NIW) library, an open-source framework for SDN/NFV metropolitan networks, created in the context of the Metro-Haul project. NIW is a library added to the Net2Plan open-source network planning software, specifically to model, provision, design and evaluate SDN/NFV networks. We introduce the major components and functionalities of NIW in a tutorial manner, including an Excel file loader meant to ease data loading for its manipulation through NIW data structure and its available methods. Finally, an illustrative example shows the basic library usage taking into account NFV over IP over WDM network resources in a reference topology.

Keywords: WDM, NFV, Open-source, Optimization, SDN.

1. INTRODUCTION

Telecom operators' networks are undergoing through a major technological breakthrough leveraging on the capabilities of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). On the one hand, SDN is based on decoupling the forwarding data-plane actions from the control-plane logical decisions [1]. On the other hand, NFV is based on implementing network functions traditionally based on bare metal hardware, as software pieces running in commodity servers [2]. NFV permits the deployment of virtualized network functions (VNFs) which can then be rapidly and flexibly instantiated, scaled up and down, in the network carrier data centers [2]. This permits the creation of Network Services (NS), which according to [3], consists of a number of VNFs, their respective order in the chain (Service Chain, SC) and the allocation of the chain in the NFV infrastructure.

SDN and NFV are complementary technologies that enable high levels of network programmability as flexible placement of VNFs can be jointly exploited with centralized traffic flow policies and (re)configurations. Indeed, the combination of SDN and NFV enables unprecedented levels of network control and dynamicity.

SDN and NFV commonly rely on the underlying IP over WDM carriers' infrastructure. Notably, the field of IP over WDM represents a research area on its own with works in the literature since the late 1990s and early 2000s [4]-[6]. Since the emergence of the IP over WDM paradigm, different research lines appeared to address specific aspects within its paradigm. For instance, [6] reviewed the most common restoration and protection schemes available at the IP and WDM layers in those years. Works within the TREND project [7][8], focused on implementing energy-aware IP-over-WDM routing solutions, leading up to recent studies such as [9], focused on estimating energy consumption in core networks.

Consequently, it is worthwhile noting that VNF instantiation and associated NS / Service Chain (SC) deployment poses an additional layer of complexity on top of the notable complex IP over WDM paradigm on its own. Authors in [10] propose an algorithm that performs dynamic service-chaining in a metro-area network jointly minimizing the average number of nodes required to host VNF instances as well as the blocking probability, although their impact is not deeply analyzed in the joint NFV placing and IP over WDM resource allocation. Relevantly, Zijian *et al.* [11] proposed an Integer Linear Program (ILP) to optimize the VNF deployment in IP over WDM networks taking into account the energy consumption.

The main contribution of this paper is the NFV over IP over WDM (NIW) library that contains in a single open-source framework all necessary tools to model SDN/NFV metropolitan networks. NIW is a library added to the Net2Plan open-source network planning software, specifically to model, provision, design and evaluate SDN/NFV-based IP over WDM networks. The main part of the paper is devoted to introduce in a tutorial manner the major components and functionalities of NIW. Subsequently, we describe an exemplary use case which contains the basic implementation of the different elements of NIW, considering IP over WDM network resources.

2. THE NIW LIBRARY: NFV OVER IP OVER WDM

The NFV over IP over WDM (NIW) Net2Plan open-source library major goals are: (i) ease algorithm development based on multiple available methods; (ii) provide a versatile framework which, based on its Excel spreadsheet importer and reporting functionalities, that permits the abstraction of the underlying representations for rapid network engineering (network capacity planning and dimensioning); and (iii) foster collaborative works

inside and outside the Metro-Haul [12] consortium following its open-source philosophy [13]. NIW is extensively documented in Javadoc format [14] and an exemplary algorithm [15].

In the following, we describe the NIW library architecture and its usage by first detailing its major elements. Finally, we present its functionality for importing data to Net2Plan via Excel spreadsheets.

2.1 NIW structure and implementation

The NIW library contains the elements illustrated in Fig. 1, which follow a tree-based class hierarchy:

- *WNet* is a class that represents a full IP over WDM network, with IT capabilities for VNF instantiation in the nodes. It provides access to all the network information and inherits all the methods and characteristics of all the other elements listed in Fig. 1 except the *Optical Spectrum Manager*.

- *WNode* models a node in the metro network. It contains network node definitions including name, type, position, population (i.e. number of users served by this node) and hardware resources availability for VNF instantiation: total amount of CPUs, RAM and HD space in the node. Nodes can be the end points of WDM links, lightpaths and IP links.

- *WFiber*, represents a unidirectional WDM optical fiber between two nodes. It is defined by origin and destination nodes and optical fiber characteristics: length (km), propagation speed, valid optical slots that the fiber propagates and physical-layer parameters (attenuation coefficient, chromatic dispersion coefficient, polarization mode dispersion PMD₀ factor). Optical slots are of 12.5 GHz width and are identified by an integer. Slot 0 has a central frequency of 193.1 THz and other slots are referenced from that baseline. The user can also specify the position of the optical line amplifiers and their gains, noise factors and PMD.

- *WIpLink* models the unidirectional part of a bidirectional IP link. It is defined by its origin and destination nodes, user-defined length (km), capacity and optionally, the lightpath that the IP link relies on. The IP link length is considered to be the physical length of the underlying lightpath, if it is realized by a lightpath, or the user-defined length mentioned above if not. *WIpLink* is represented by *Link* in the IP layer GUI of Net2Plan.

- *WLightpathRequest* is the *intent* or request to establish a lightpath in the network. It is defined by the origin and destination nodes, line rate (Gbps) and the requisite or not to be realized with 1+1 optical protection.

- *WLightpathUnregenerated* represents a lightpath satisfying a particular lightpath request, without optical-electrical-optical (OEO) regeneration in any intermediate node. It is defined by the sequence of fibers (*WFiber*) traversed, that make a path between the lightpath request end nodes. It is also characterized by the optical spectrum occupied in the traversed fibers, given as the identifiers of the occupied optical slots. Note that the model permits flexi-grid and mixed-line rate networks. *WLightpathUnregenerated* elements are represented as *Route* elements in the WDM layer of the Net2Plan GUI.

- *WServiceChainRequest* models the request for deploying an *anycast* SC. A SC request is characterized by a set of potential origin nodes, a set of potential destination nodes, the sequence of *types* of VNFs to traverse, and the amount of traffic injected in the origin of the chain. This traffic can be disseminated in different time slots, thus representing user-defined multi-hour traffic scenarios. The chain is also characterized by latency constraints imposed to the SCs satisfying this request, given by the maximum latency values from the origin node to entry of each VNF in the chain. Also, it is possible to specify compression factors of the traffic when traversing each VNF. For instance, if a VNF in the chain is expected to compress the traversing IP traffic, its compressing factor can be introduced as a parameter in the SC request, and automatically applied by the library. SC requests appear as *Demand* objects at the IP layer of the Net2Plan GUI.

- *WServiceChain* represents a SC satisfying a SC request. The SC is a sequence of IP links and VNF instances that (i) starts in one of the request origin nodes, (ii) ends in one of the request end nodes, and (iii) traverses the ordered set of VNF instances commanded by the chain request. The initially injected traffic can be user defined, so the occupied resources at the traversed IP links and VNF instances are automatically updated.

- *WVnfType* is a user-defined type of VNF that can be later used as part of SCs. Examples may be: transcoder, firewall, NAT, DHCP, etc. A *WVnfType* is characterized by a processing time, a maximum amount of IP traffic that it can process, and the amount of CPUs, RAM and HD space consumed. The user can also add VNF instantiation constraints, by specifying the set of nodes where VNFs of this type can be instantiated.

- *WVnfInstance* models a particular instantiation, in a particular node, of a VNF of a particular type. VNF instances can be traversed by SCs, summing up as much IP traffic as the one specified by its type.

- *WUserService* represents information of a user service that can be defined in the network and used to automatically populate the network with SC requests. A user service can be e.g. “videoconference”, or “Web surfing”. User services are bidirectional. Upstream traffic originates in the user, and ends in the network, and

Fig. 1. NIW library elements and their tree-based class hierarchy.

downstream traffic ends in the user, and is originated in the network. The characteristics of upstream and downstream traffic can be defined individually.

- *OpticalSpectrumManager* is used to account for the occupation of the optical spectrum in the network, e.g. informing of spectrum clashing, and providing useful methods for solving several routing and spectrum assignment problem variants.

2.2 Excel file importer

The NIW library includes an Excel file importer functionality [13]. As listed in Table I, the Excel file is based on a five-tab structure with a specific scheme to be consumed and processed by NIW. The goal of the Excel file is to include enough information for (i) defining an IP over WDM network topology with IT resources in the nodes, and (ii) defining a set of user services, their VNF types to traverse, and their traffic intensity, potentially with time-varying intensities. The NIW library converts such Excel-based human-readable scenario into a Net2Plan network instance NIW-compatible.

In each tab, a given set and order of parameters needs to be maintained, being the information within each parameter mandatory or optional. For instance, origin and destination of a fiber need to be indicated whereas its bidirectionality is optional.

The *Nodes* tab specifies the set of nodes deployed in the network. Nodes can be tagged as being connected to the core network or not (*isConnectedToCoreNode* attribute). This is used in MetroHaul project where two types of metro nodes are considered: metro core edge nodes (MCEN) and access metro edge nodes (AMEN). AMENs are never connected to the core, while MCENs can optionally be.

The *VnfTypes* tab permits to set a variety of VNF definitions with user-defined parameters of each instance (GBs, CPU, RAM, HD and processing time). Relevantly, the instantiation of *VnfTypes* can be limited by the user to specific nodes using the boolean parameter *Constrained to some nodes?*. In case it applies (i.e. true value), a list of valid nodes for instantiation can be also defined per *VnfType* with *Nodes valid for instantiation* column.

The *User Services* tab defines the following parameters for each Service Name (e.g. video, VoIP, gaming). *List VNF upstream* and *List VNF downstream* show the sequence of VNF types to traverse in each direction by the service. *Traffic Expansion Up* and *Traffic Expansion Down* are used to scale (indicated as a factor) the traffic after each traversed VNF with respect to the initial traffic. This permits representing VNFs that e.g. compress the traffic when traversed. Similarly, but in terms of latency, *MaxLatency_Up* and *MaxLatency_Down* define the maximum acceptable delay to reach each VNF in the sequence of the SC. *InjectionDownExpansion* models the traffic injected by the destination node in the downstream direction with respect to the initial traffic in the upstream direction.

The *PerNodeAndServiceTimeIntensity* tab is used to define the traffic behavior of each service over time. The *ServiceChainInjectionNodeUniqueName* and *ServiceUniqueId* parameters are jointly used to specify per each node and service type pair the traffic injected into the network. *TrafficInjection* is composed of multiple columns to specify the traffic injection factor for user-defined time periods (e.g. day composed of morning, afternoon, night; week; month), giving the possibility to model the traffic in a free way and without fixed column restrictions. Additional information can be found in an exemplary Excel file [16].

3. EXEMPLARY USE CASE IN NIW

In this section, we describe an exemplary use case to illustrate the applicability of the main methods provided by NIW. The final approach of this use case is generating a network representation containing network services using NFV over an IP over WDM infrastructure.

Specifically, the implementation of the sequence of actions in this use case is shown in Algorithm 1 and, using available NIW methods, performs the following seven logical steps: (i) import the topology from Excel file using the *importFromExcelFile* method and create the Optical Spectrum Manager (OSM), which is in charge of managing the available optical spectrum to be used; (ii) for each pair of nodes, line 4 finds the shortest WDM path (*getKShortestWdmPath*) and then in line 7 a lightpath (*addLightpathUnregenerated*) is created occupying and reserving some of the available slots in OSM (*allocateOccupation*); after that (iii) line 9 creates an IP link between that origin node (n_o) and destination node (n_d) using *addIpLink* and couple the previous lightpath

TABLE I
EXCEL FILE IMPORTER FIVE-TAB STRUCTURE AND ATTRIBUTES

Tab	Parameters
Nodes	Name, Longitude, Latitude, Type, isConnectedToCoreNode, NodeBasePopulation, TotalNumCPUs, TotalRAM_GB, TotalHD_GB, ArbitraryParams*
Fibers	Origin, Destination, Length**, Bidirectional?*, Slot Ranges, Attenuation Coeff, Chromatic dispersion Coeff, PMD design value, Amplifier Positions, Amplifier Gains, Amplifier Noise dB, Amplifier Pmd, ArbitraryParams*
Vnf Types	VnfType (name), VnfInstanceCapacity_Gbps, OccupCPU, OccupRAM_GB, OccupHD_GB, Processing_time_inMs, Constrained to some nodes?*, Nodes valid for instantiation, ArbitraryParams*
User Services	Service Name, List VNF upstream, List VNF downstream, TrafficExpansion_UP, TrafficExpansion_DOWN, MaxLatency_UP, MaxLatency_DOWN, InjectionDownExpansion, Ending in core node?*, ArbitraryParams*
PerNodeAndServiceTimeIntensity	ServiceChainInjectionNodeUniqueName, ServiceUniqueId, TrafficInjection

* Optional attribute.

**If the value is -1, Net2Plan will automatically calculates the length considering Harversine formula.

created into it (*coupleToIpLink*). At this point the IP over WDM coupling is achieved; (iv) for each service previously loaded from the Excel file or created by coding manually, retrieving in line 12 the list of VNFs to traverse using *getListVnfTypesToTraverseUpstream*; (v) instantiate an VNFs in a specific node using *addVnfInstance* method. This way, an user-defined standalone VNF instantiation can be deployed uncoupling the decision to the SC and then (vi) in line 16 a SC request is created from an origin node that intends to generate traffic for a specific service (*addServiceChainRequest*). In order to satisfy that demand, the shortest path between n_o and n_d in the IP layer is needed, so *getKShortestServiceChainInIpLayer* is used. Once the path is calculated by Net2Plan, the remaining step (vii) is to finally add this SC through the *addServiceChain* method shown in line 18. The user is encouraged to explore the help examples shipped with the NIW release in Net2Plan. Examples illustrate how NIW can be used to create resource allocation and capacity planning schemes in one or more levels of the NFV over IP over WDM infrastructure.

```

1:wNet = ImportMetroNetwork.importFromExcelFile(excelPath);
2:osm = OpticalSpectrumManager.createFromRegularLps(wNet);
3:foreach <no,nd> ∈ N×N
4:  wdmPaths = wNet.getKShortestWdmPath(K, no, destination);
5:  lpr = wNet.addLightpathRequest(no, nd, linerate);
6:  wl = osm.spectrumAssignment_firstFit(link,slots);
7:  lp = lpr.addLightpathUnregenerated(wdmPath, wl);
8:  osm.allocateOccupation(lp, link, wl);
9:  ipLink = wNet.addIpLink(no, nd, linerate);
10: lpr.coupleToIpLink(ipLink.getFirst());
11: foreach service ∈ S
12:   vnfs = service.getListVnfTypesToTraverseUpstream();
13:   foreach vnf ∈ V
14:     wNet.addVnfInstance(node, vnf);
15:   end foreach
16:   scr = wNet.addServiceChainRequest(node, service);
17:   ipPaths = wNet.getKShortestServiceChainInIpLayer(K, no, nd, scr);
18:   scr.addServiceChain(ipPath, traffic);
19: end foreach
20:end foreach

```

Algorithm 1. Pseudo-code of a NIW library exemplary use case.

4. CONCLUSIONS

SDN and NFV are two complementary promising technologies to address the challenging 5G scenario. In this paper, we introduce the NIW library, a Net2Plan-based open-source framework targeted for modelling, provisioning, designing and evaluating NFV over IP over WDM networks. Through the paper, we described NIW covering its major elements, methods and its Excel importer functionality. We also provide an exemplary use case to illustrate the usage of the NIW library, including a didactic algorithm addressing the allocation of SCs via instantiation of multiple VNFs in data centers connected in an IP over WDM network, also allocating the inter-data center network resources.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported in part by the Spanish Government for the ONOFRE-2 project under Grant TEC2017-84423-C3-2-P (MINECO/AEI/FEDER, UE) and the Elastic Networks project under Grant TEC2015-71932-REDT, and by the European Commission for the H2020-ICT-2016-2 METRO-HAUL project (G. A. 761727) and the H2020-MSCA-IF-2016 INSPIRING-SNI project (G. A. 750611).

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Kreutz, *et al.* "Software-defined networking: A comprehensive survey," *Proc. IEEE*, v. 103(1), pp. 14–76, 2015.
- [2] M. Chiosi *et al.*, "Network functions virtualisation: An introduction, benefits, enablers, challenges and call for action," [Online]. Available: http://portal.etsi.org/NFV/NFV_White_Paper.pdf
- [3] J. G. Herrera, *et al.* "Resource allocation in NFV: A comprehensive survey," *Tran. Net. Service Manag.*, v.13(3), 2016.
- [4] X. Zhang, *et al.* "On Fundamental Issues in IP over WDM Multicast," *ICCCN*, Boston, MA, USA, 11-13 Oct. 1999.
- [5] N. Ghani, *et al.* "On IP-over-WDM Integration," *Published in IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 38(3), Mar. 2000.
- [6] A. Fumagalli, *et al.* "IP restoration vs. WDM protection: is there an optimal choice?," *IEEE Network*, vol. 14(6), 2000.
- [7] F. Idzikowski, *et al.* "TREND in Energy-Aware Adaptive Routing Solutions," *IEEE Com. Mag.*, v.51(11), Nov 2013.
- [8] M. Ajmone, *et al.* "TREND: Toward real energy-efficient network design," *SustainIT*, Pisa, Italy, Oct. 2012.
- [9] H. Alharbi, *et al.* "Real-Time Emissions of Telecom Core Networks," *ICTON*, Bucharest, Rumania, July 2018.
- [10] L. Askari, *et al.* "VNF placement for dynamic service chaining in metro-area network," *ONDM*, Dublin, Ireland, 2018.
- [11] Z. Yang, *et al.* "VNF Placement for Service Chaining in IP over WDM Networks", *ACP*, Hangzhou, China, Oct. 2018.
- [12] Metro-Haul project. [Online]. <https://metro-haul.eu/>.
- [13] NFV over IP over WDM (NIW) library. [Online]. Available. <https://github.com/girtel/Net2Plan/.../niw/networkModel>.
- [14] NIW Javadoc documentation. [Online]. Available: <http://www.net2plan.com/documentation/.../>.
- [15] NIW library sample algorithm. [Online]. Available. <https://github.com/girtel/Net2Plan/.../TutorialAlgorithm.java>.
- [16] Excel file template of the NIW library. [Online]. Available: https://github.com/girtel/.../MetroNetwork_Template.xlsx.